

Recommended citation: Yeh, L. -, Tai, C. -, & Chen, C. -. (2017). Investigation of a Line-Tracing Auto Guided Vehicle as an Educational Tool for Mechatronics . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 1417-1425). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698577.

Investigation of a Line-Tracing Auto Guided Vehicle as an Educational Tool for Mechatronics

Long-Jyi Yeh¹, Ching-Chih Tai¹, Chih-Yun Chen¹

Professor / chairman of department, professor, student

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Tatung University, Taiwan, ROC

E-mail: ljyeh@ttu.edu.tw, cctai@ttu.edu.tw, spyk369121@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Department of Mechanical Engineering bears responsibility of automation engineering training, and one related courses is Mechatronics. The author uses the line-tracing auto guided vehicle (LT-AGV) as a Mechatronics course teaching tool for more than ten years. The purpose of this research is to enhance the teaching content of a LT-AGV. The LT-AGV serving as an educational tool is divided into two parts. The first part is the mechanism design of an AGV and the second part is the AGV's control circuit design and implementation. In order to upgrade the LT-AGV's system, plenty engineering designs and manufacturing methods have been developed to improve students' learning outcomes in this research. An experimental analysis method is used to find out the difference of the design parameters through verifying the performance of LT-AGV. After comparing the experimental data of AGV's performance, a more suitable range of design parameters was proposed. Consequently, the investigation of design parameters on the LT-AGV had been accomplished. This new LT-AGV system can serve as an useful tool in teaching.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development; Attractiveness of Engineering Education; Engineering Education Research

Keywords: *line-tracing auto guided vehicle (LT-AGV); educational tool; mechatronics.*

INTRODUCTION

A Line-Tracing Auto Guided Vehicle (LT-AGV) system was developed in a Mechatronics course. This course has been developed for more than a decade. A black curve with 35 mm width is printed on an A0-size white paper (841x1189) to be used as the LT-AGV test track. The test track becomes more and more complex over the past 10 years as shown in Figure 1. The progress of this course in teaching is therefore verified.

The course is constructed by two phases. The first phase is a practice course and the second phase is basic lectures. For the first phase, all the students are asked to make a LT-AGV according to teacher's guidance. Through learning by doing, students can establish the complete concept of an automation system and apply knowledge of basic electrical principle. For the basic lecture

¹ Corresponding Author : Long-Jyi Yeh,
e-mail address : ljyeh@ttu.edu.tw

Fig. 1. (a)~(c) Test track of 2005, 2011, and 2015. It is printed on A0-size paper. And (d) the easy runway is also prepared for the low performance LT-AGVs.

Fig. 2. Various AGVs made by students(a, b) and the test scene (c)

in second phase, the lecture material will focus on the automatic system's concept and the introduction of the sensor, the controller, the actuator [1], and the LT-AGV design and manufacture. In the course of this implementation, the study of LT-AGV's performances includes the AGV design, kinetic analysis, the friction force, the wheel, the vehicle speed, and the vehicle turning. Figure 2 shows various LT-AGVs that were made by students and the test scene.

1. The Design Parameters and Related Electrical Circuits of the AGV

1.1 The Structure and Design Parameters of the AGV

In order to explore the influence of geometric parameters on the AGV's line-tracing ability, a prototype of the educational AGV that can flexibly adjust the geometric parameters is constructed and shown in Figure 3. The illustration of this AGV is shown in Figure 4.

A pair of sensors were used to detect the black track (test runway) which is to be followed. A controller is used to receive signal feed back from the sensors and to submit a command to drive DC motors mounted on both sides of the AGV. When one side of the DC motor stops but the other is running, the AGV will turn. All of these will be properly presented on the basic lecture of this course to teach students to design an AGV with superior performance [2~4].

According to experimental observation, the geometric parameters of the AGV will influence the AGV's ability to turn. Therefore, in order to improve the AGV's line-tracing performance, four kinds of geometric parameters were chosen as shown in Figure 4. Which are : **A**: the distance between the motor's wheel and the universal wheel; **B**: the distance between the motor's wheel and the photo sensor;

(a) Top view

(b) Side view

(c) bottom view

Fig. 3. The LT-AGV used to experiment and its four kinds of geometric design parameters.

C: the distance between two photo sensors; **D**: the distance between two motor wheels. These parameters must be carefully considered in the design and manufacture process of a LT-AGV. It is easy to understand that the design parameter C depends on the width of the track (black line). Parameter A is a secondary parameter that is less relevant to AGV's motion effects.

1.2 Electrical Circuits of the AGV

The illustration of line-tracing concept is shown in Figure 5. The sensor module can be set over the black track (Run By Black ; RBB mode) or beside the black track (Run By White ; RBW mode). In the case of RBB mode shown in Figure 5 (a), when the right side sensor module exceeds the black track and senses the white **background**, the controller should stop the **left side** motor to turn AGV left. On the other case of RBW mode shown in Figure 5 (b), when the right side sensor module senses the **black track** the controller should stop the

Fig. 4. The illustration of AGV and its four kinds of geometric design parameters.

Fig. 5. The illustration of AGV running mode. (Note the location of sensors)

right side motor to turn AGV right.

The photo resistor is adopted as a sensor in the LT-AGV system and is integrated into a sensor module with a LED to avoid the interference of the environment light. The detail is shown in Figure 6.

In addition, both LM358 (operational amplifier) and 2SC1384 (transistor) serve as a controller. The DC motor is the actuator. Subsequently, these components will be the control system that manipulates the AGV's motion. There are two types of control circuit that can be used, as shown in Figure 7. The first one is the RBB mode as shown in Figure 5 (a). In this case, the control circuit is shown in Figure 7 (a). When the photo resistor senses the black track, the weak reflection makes resistance of photo resistor higher and induces voltage V_s higher than V_{ref} . The comparator (LM358) outputs a high voltage to make transistor (2SC1384) switch on. Then the motor runs. Once the photo resistor goes out of the black track and senses the white background, the motor stops. The other case is RBW mode as shown in Figure 7 (b). In this mode, when the photo resistor senses the white background of the black track, the intense reflection makes resistance of photo resistor lower and induces voltage V_s lower than V_{ref} .

Fig. 6. Photo resistor transfers the light intensity to a voltage output with voltage divider. The sensor module includes the LED and photoresistor are covered by a 3D printed white case.

Fig. 7. Two types of control circuit for the LT-AGV. Student can choose one of them to implement.

The comparator (LM358) outputs a high voltage to make transistor (2SC1384) to switch on. Then the motor runs. Once photo resistor senses the black track below it, the motor stops.

2. An Assessment of the Ranges of AGV's Design Parameters

2.1 AGV's Design Parameters

In addition to the geometric design parameters defined in Section 1.1 (Fig. 4.), the speed and the stop characteristic of the LT-AGV are also the important factors. It will be consistent with our driving experience, when the speed is too fast the car will not be easy to turn. In addition, when the car's braking force is insufficient, the car will become difficult to drive when turning. To assess the performance of the LT-AGV, the effects of speed and the kinetic parameter (an AGV's moving distance after the motor stops) must be studied at first.

2.2 The Test Track's Dimension and Curve Design

To understand the influence of the AGV's design parameters on its turning performance, twelve kinds of track turning radii (45 mm, 50 mm, 55 mm, 60 mm, 65 mm, 70 mm, 75 mm, 80 mm, 85 mm, 90 mm, 117.5 mm, and 127.5mm) are selected in the experimental study. The turning angle is preset at 90 degrees.

2.3 The Influence of the Moving Distance (L) on the AGV's Curve-Turning Ability

The kinetic motion of the LT-AGV controlled by the RBB mode is depicted in Fig. 8. As indicated in Fig. 8(b), the right side sensor will exceed the track line when the black track turns left. The signal emitted from the right sensor module will be forwarded to the controller to stop the left motor and the LT-AGV will turn left. However, because of the internal effect of the motor driving system, the motor will keep rotating for a while. This will result in continuous movement for the AGV even though the motor is stop. The continuous movement is called *the moving distance (L)* [3].

Fig. 8. The kinetic motion of the LT-AGV controlled by the RBB mode.

It is obvious from the figure, the left sensor will also exceed the black track if the L is too long. This will result in the motors stopping at the right and left wheels. Thus, the AGV's track-turning motion will fail. Therefore, to assure a successful tracking on a turning track line, the experimental assessment of an appropriate L at various turning radius of the track line is essential.

In order to measure a longer moving distance (L), a long straight track shown in Fig.9 is constructed. Here, the AGV's velocity depends on the motor's working voltages. Various working voltages can be obtained by connecting various numbers of diodes in a series to the electrical circuit. The related moving distance (L) and available radius of the curved track with respect to various AGV velocities will be obtained by using the experimental tests.

An experimental test of the moving distance (L) with respect to the available radii of curved tracks is performed and the results are shown in Table 1. As indicated in Table 1, the available radius of the curved track will increase if the moving distance (L) increases. A comparison of a maximum reacting distance for the two kinds of AGV's line-tracing control algorithms is inspected and illustrated in **Fig. 10**. Result in the RBB mode has a smaller reacting distance than that of the RBW. Therefore, the probability of a larger reacting distance to successfully pass through a curved track line is higher than that of the smaller reacting distance.

Table 1. An experimental test of the moving distance (L) with respect to curved radii.

Electrical voltage (V)	L (mm)	R^*
2.2	16	50
3.2	38	85
4.2	70	127.5

Note : the R^* is the smallest curve track radii that the AGV can successfully pass (mm)

Fig. 9. The experimental testing of the AGV on a straight track.

(a) maximum reacting distance for RBB mode (b) maximum reacting distance for RBW mode

Fig. 10. The comparison of maximum reacting distance for two kinds of AGV's line-tracing controlling algorithms.

As a geometrical check, both sensors are limited within the black line when using the first algorithm. Conversely, the setting of the sensors' locations will be easily performed with a sufficient space that is away from the black line when using the RBW mode. Hence, in the AGV's educational practice course, the old line-tracing algorithm will be replaced by the ***“run for white line and stop for black line”*** i.e. RBW mode.

2.4 The Influence of Geometric Design Parameters

Experimental tests for the wheel's distance and track turning is performed and shown in Table 2. Both the wheels' distance (D) and the AGV's velocity are selected as the variables. Here, the AGV's velocity will be adjusted by varying the motor's working voltage. As in Section 2.3, the working voltage can be reduced by connecting the diodes in series to the electrical circuit. As indicated in Table 2, the curved track's turning ability will decrease a little when the wheels' distance (D) increases. However, the influence of curved track's turning ability is not obvious if the wheel distance (D) decreases. This is because the wheel distance will be constrained by the motor's gear box. Consequently, the experimental results revealed that an appropriate range of the wheel distance (D) is between **95~115 mm**.

Because of the space limitations of this article, the experimental data of other parameters on the performance of the LT-AGV are not described here, only the final results. The complete experimental study process and results will be published in a full paper in the future. Here, the experimental results reveal that an appropriate range of parameter B is between 30~50 mm. With this, the line-tracing and curved track-turning in a hairpin track will be successful.

Consequently, based on the experimental results and assessment of the LT-AGV's parameters, four observing aspects that can improve the LT-AGV's line-trace performances are listed below.

- (1) The curved track's turning ability will increase when the moving distance (L) decreases. The recommended L is below 4 mm.
- (2) The curved track's turning ability will be improved if the wheels' distance (D) decreases.

Table 2. Experimental test for the wheel's distance (D) and track turning.

case	MWV	D	R*	case	MWV	D	R*	Note 1
1	A	95	55	9	C	115	127.5	D:Wheel's distance (mm)
2	B	95	90	10	A	125	55	R*:The smallest curved track's turning radii that AGV can successfully pass (mm)
3	C	95	127.5	11	B	125	85	
4	A	105	55	12	C	125	X	
5	B	105	85	13	A	140	60	X:fail to pass the turning radius of 127.5mm
6	C	105	127.5	14	B	140	90	
7	A	115	55	15	C	140	X	
8	B	115	85					

Note 2. MWV (Motor Working Voltage): A (working voltage: 4.3V , higher AGV speed) ; B (working voltage: 3.6V) ; C (working voltage: 2.9V , lower speed)

(3) The curved track's turning ability for the hairpin track will be improved if the distance between the sensor and the wheel (B) is between 30~50 mm.

The observation and discussion above can serve as design guidelines in a preliminary Mechatronics course. With this, an advanced electrical circuit design will be further developed in the future.

3. Conclusion

This study proposed that LT-AGV is an effective educational tool for the Mechatronic curriculum and should be the core of teaching. It integrates: (1) the concept of SCAM system chain (Sensor→ Controller→Actuator → Mechanism) for teaching and new course content; (2) Ohm's law and voltage divider circuit applications (3) the knowledge of the transistor in the electronics and its control circuit of the DC motor; (4) the application of the operational amplifier as a comparator in electronics.

Best of all, in the LT-AGV control circuit, because photo resistor is susceptible to ambient light, students are enforced to solve this problem and repeatedly adjust the variable resistor of the control circuit to make their LT-AGV work. In such a process, the students must take the initiative to understand the principles of the control circuit, and then it becomes possible to adjust a good function of the LT-AGV, thus ensuring the effectiveness of teaching.

In addition, LT-AGV on the road test movement characteristics are very complex. In fact, it is difficult to explain very clearly. However, through the implementation and practice, as long as they follow proposed procedures and adjustment guidance, students can complete a good functional LT-AGV. In accordance with the proposed procedure and the adjustment method proposed by this study, students are inspired by the process of **learning by doing** in the application of mechanics and kinematics.

The author would like to thank his college for various supports in teaching and research over the past 20 years.

References

- [1] Thomas L. Floyd, Digital Fundamentals with VHDL, Prentice Hall , 2003.
- [2] Long-Jyi Yeh, Lecture 1: Mechatronics Course, Tatung University, 2014.
- [3] Chia-Yun Hsiang, A development and design of an educational carrier for mechatronics, Master thesis, Tatung University, 2015. (小向)
- [4] Kenneth J. Waldron, Gary L. Kinzel and Sunil K. Agrawal, Kinematics, dynamics, and design of machinery, Wiley, 2016.